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Research Article

**A RESEARCH STUDY ON OSTEOPOROSIS IN PATIENTS OF
PEPTIC ULCER ILLNESS****Dr. Saba Mahmood, Dr. Maham Zeba, Dr. Fatima Hunnain**
House Officer, Jinnah Hospital, Lahore.**Article Received:** February 2019**Accepted:** March 2019**Published:** April 2019**Abstract:**

Background: Osteoporosis amongst peptic ulcer sickness remains one of difficulties frequently described. **Objective:** The objective of our current research was to regulate occurrence of osteoporosis in cases by peptic ulcer sickness.

Methodology: This research remained evocative, cross sectional research that remained led at Mayo Hospital Lahore from March to September 2018. In our current research study patients of age 19 years or else extra identified by peptic ulcer illness on past also then long-established on higher GI endoscopy, remained comprised. Those patients remained then measured on DEXA scan in addition osteoporosis stayed considered as yes anywhere here remained notch of fewer than 3.6. Information remained arrived in addition examined by using SPSS version 22.

Results: In our current research study here remained whole 65 patients out of which 31 remained men in addition, 33 women. The average age remained 44.24 ± 9.14 years. The average period of PUD remained 4.3 ± 0.32 years also average T score remained 2.3 ± 0.9 . Osteoporosis stayed understood in 5 (7.68%) of patients. Osteoporosis remained extra understood in women upsetting 04 (10.39%) patients of them individual sets ($p = 0.03$). Here remained not any substantial alteration in rapports of period of PUD by osteoporosis ($p = 0.87$).

Conclusion: Osteoporosis stays freshly researched problem of peptic ulcer illness also is not actual known, but then again still existing amongst numerous patients of peptic ulcer sickness as shown by our research.

Key words: Peptic ulcer disease, GI Endoscopy, Osteoporosis, DEXA seen.

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INTRODUCTION:

Epigastric discomfort remains one of maximum common exhibitions in medicinal OPD also emergencies. Peptic ulcer disease (PUD) stays one of the main reasons foremost to epigastric discomfort, laterally by gastro esophageal reflux. PUD remains produced through inequity among acid making also usual defensive instruments in addition lead to damage in inferior fragment of esophagus, stomach or else previous share of minor intestine; cooperatively called as peptic part [1]. This might delay by numerous purposes of stomach in addition, principal to alteration problems in addition add to additional illness. Here remain multiple influences fluctuating from life elegances to diverse medications that may affect over this also led to the break in mucosa. In existing research osteoporosis in patients of peptic ulcer illness remained detected in 5 (7.68%) in total of 65 patients [2]. Those outcomes remained also alike to our research completed through Sawicki et al, anywhere it remained gotten in around 6% of patients also they similarly extra observed for its suggestion also it remained detected that here remains double the risk of osteoporosis in cases that have PUD as associated to these who haven't this. Occurrence of co morbid situations comparable Hypertension in addition DM likewise controlled to even developed degree of this difficulty in the current research [3]. In our current research study, woman sex exposed expressively developed degree of the current difficulty in difference to men anywhere it pretentious 04 (10.39%) patients as associated to 2 (4.58%) man in its separate sets through substantial alteration. ($p=0.03$). Those comprise life style change, amplified beverages usage, chocolates, smoking, also alcohol. Numerous medications remain also culprit for this also NSAIDs being maximum disreputable ones [4]. H pylori remains greatest researched bug that stays originate in intestinal also lead to wound of mucosa. Osteoporosis remains well distinct as an object that label condensed bone mineralization. Widespread pains also caution particularly at bony parts also occasionally impulsive fracture remain hallmark scientific exhibitions. It might remain identified on numerous methods also analytic tests also basic them remains to classify bone marrow thickness [5]. The danger issues for osteoporosis comprise woman sex, DM, smoking also reduced consumption of calcium. Here remain so numerous additional issues that have been inconsistently related by the current problem also not well researched also have shown adjustable suggestion by this [6]. Peptic ulcer illness, long term proton pump inhibitors stay also one of them. The information has exposed occurrence of osteoporosis from 10.36% to 21.6% in patients with peptic ulcer illness. The key

aim of our current research remained to regulate incidence of osteoporosis in cases having peptic ulcer illness.

METHODOLOGY:

Research sceneries: Mayo Hospital Lahore.

Research period: March to September 2018.

Research enterprise: Cross sectional study.

Sampling technique: Non-probability successive sample.

In current research study, 65 patients of peptic ulcer illness remained comprised afterward captivating knowledgeable agreement. Thorough sociodemographic also medical information remained composed. Peptic ulcer sickness remained identified through signs of epigastric aching besides sweltering sense for at least extra than 4 months. In existing research osteoporosis in patients of peptic ulcer illness remained detected in 5 (7.68%) in total of 65 patients. Those outcomes remained also alike to our research completed through Sawicki et al, anywhere it remained gotten in around 6% of patients also they similarly extra observed for its suggestion also it remained detected that here remains double the risk of osteoporosis in cases that have PUD as associated to these who haven't this. Occurrence of co morbid situations comparable Hypertension in addition DM likewise controlled to even developed degree of this difficulty in the current research. In our current research study, woman sex exposed expressively developed degree of the current difficulty in difference to men anywhere it pretentious 04 (10.39%) patients as associated to 2 (4.58%) man in its separate sets through substantial alteration. ($p=0.03$). This remained likewise showed by additional researches as well thru Cappuccino FP et al. also, Tsuda K et al, who likewise originate woman sex as advanced prone to the difficulty. Altogether grownups of age 19 also extra remained encompassed also these by co morbid comparable DM, hypertension smoking also analyzed distortion or else long-lasting liver before renal illness remained excepted. Those patients remained experienced higher gastrointestinal endoscopy to settle the peptic ulcer. Also, these by long-established PUD remained measured through DEXA scan to branded osteoporosis current. The score of < 3.6 remained labeled as yes. Information remained arrived also examined using SPSS version 22.0. Post stratification chi square test stayed practical also the worth of < 0.06 stayed taken as substantial.

RESULTS:

In the current research study, here remained 65 patients, out of those 31 remained men also 35 women. The average age remained 44.25 ± 9.14 years. The

average period of PUD remained 4.3 ± 0.32 years also the average T score stayed 2.3 ± 0.9 . Osteoporosis remained understood in 5 (7.68%) of patients. Osteoporosis remained extra in women moving 04 (10.39%) patients ($p = 0.03$). Occurrence of co morbid situations comparable Hypertension in addition DM likewise controlled to even developed degree of this difficulty in the current research. In our current research study, woman sex exposed expressively developed degree of the current difficulty in difference to men anywhere it pretentious 04 (10.39%) patients as associated to 2 (4.58%) man in its separate sets

through substantial alteration. ($p=0.03$). This remained likewise showed by additional researches as well thru Cappuccino FP et al. also, Tsuda K et al, who likewise originate woman sex as advanced prone to the difficulty. Altogether grownups of age 19 also extra remained encompassed also these by co morbid comparable DM, hypertension smoking also analyzed distortion or else long-lasting liver before renal illness remained excepted. Here remained not any substantial alteration in rappsots of period of PUD by osteoporosis ($p= 0.87$) as in table 1.

Table 1: Osteoporosis through deference to gender also period of peptic ulcer illness.

Variables	Osteoporosis		P-value
	Yes No (%)	No No (%)	
Sex	Men	03 (9.38%)	0.86
	Women	01 (3.57%)	
Duration of PUD	< 2 years	2(7.15%)	0.02
	< 2 years	2 (6.25%)	

DISCUSSION:

Reduced bone inorganic thickness principal to reduced bone strength in addition lead to osteoporosis that remains branded through widespread aches in addition efforts also might uniform principal to impulsive fractures as well. Peptic ulcer illness remains underneath widespread conversation in the current periods to aspect for its overtone through osteoporosis [7]. In existing research osteoporosis in patients of peptic ulcer illness remained detected in 5 (7.68%) in total of 65 patients. Those outcomes remained also alike to our research completed through Sawicki et al, anywhere it remained gotten in around 6% of patients also they similarly extra observed for its suggestion also it remained detected that here remains double the risk of osteoporosis in cases that have PUD as associated to these who haven't this [8]. Occurrence of co morbid situations comparable Hypertension in addition DM likewise controlled to even developed degree of this difficulty in the current research. In our current research study, woman sex exposed expressively developed degree of the current difficulty in difference to men anywhere it pretentious 04 (10.39%) patients as associated to 2 (4.58%) man in its separate sets through substantial alteration. ($p=0.03$). This remained likewise showed by additional researches as well thru Cappuccino FP et al. also, Tsuda K et al, who likewise originate woman sex as advanced prone to the difficulty [9]. This discovery might remain designated or else clarified through influence that women remain extra susceptible owing to numerous hormonal issues i.e. throughout

menopause also at developed ages danger of osteoporosis remains previously in height in women as associated to men. Unexpectedly some researches exposed advanced quantity of such patients in man sex. Wu CH et al, in their research exposed that man sex exposed the improved connotation by osteoporosis as associated to women in PUD nonetheless they did not discover the current connotation as substantial [10]. This might delay by numerous purposes of stomach in addition, principal to alteration problems in addition add to additional illness. Here remain multiple influences fluctuating from life elegances to diverse medications that may affect over this also led to the break in mucosa. In existing research osteoporosis in patients of peptic ulcer illness remained detected in 5 (7.68%) in total of 65 patients. Those outcomes remained also alike to our research completed through Sawicki et al, anywhere it remained gotten in around 6% of patients also they similarly extra observed for its suggestion also it remained detected that here remains double the risk of osteoporosis in cases that have PUD as associated to these who haven't this [11]. Occurrence of co morbid situations comparable Hypertension in addition DM likewise controlled to even developed degree of this difficulty in the current research. In our current research study, woman sex exposed expressively developed degree of the current difficulty in difference to men anywhere it pretentious 04 (10.39%) patients as associated to 2 (4.58%) man in its separate sets through substantial alteration. ($p=0.03$). Those comprise life style change, amplified beverages usage,

chocolates, smoking, also alcohol. The motive of this in man sex might be mostly of 2 issues; smoking also H Pylori contamination. This remained showed through the research completed through Figure et al, that exposed that men remain extra diseased through H pylori contagion that women also lead to widespread illness in form of PUD which remains nowadays related by osteoporosis. Laszlo et al, measured testosterone another danger influence to move gastric ulceration also henceforth osteoporosis in the research study.

CONCLUSION:

The current research study presented that osteoporosis which stays freshly researched trouble of peptic ulcer illness also remains not selfsame common, nevertheless still occurrence as shown in the current research study.

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